

Serbia

This report describes the structure of the national higher education system in Serbia, focusing on the institutional types as defined by national categories. It builds on the Eurydice Report on the national higher education system and complements it with quantitative information on the role of higher education institution (HEI) types in the national system, based on data derived from the European Tertiary Education Register (<http://www.eter-project.eu>) for the period 2013-2020.

Types of Higher Education Institutions

According to Eurydice¹, the Serbian higher education system comprises four types of HEIs:

- Universities,
- Colleges of Applied Studies,
- Colleges of academic studies,
- Academies of Applied Studies.

According to the way of their foundation, HEIs are either public or private institutions. Public higher education institutions are established by the state. Higher education institutions founded by an autonomous legal entity, or a private person are private HEIs. Both types of HEIs become legal entities within the higher education system in Serbia only after receiving a state permission granted by the Ministry of Education, Science and Technological Development.

Every accredited higher education institution in Serbia can organise study programmes and issue first and second-cycle degree certificates (academic and professional), but only universities can implement third-cycle educational programmes. In general, an HEI cannot become a university unless it offers doctoral studies in at least three fields (natural sciences and mathematics, social sciences and humanities, medical science, technical and technological sciences and arts). In addition, a difference between universities and other HEIs in Serbia is also reflected by the fact that universities are obligated to be engaged in research - their teachers must have appropriate ranking in the scientific community and apply their scientific knowledge and research results in relevant educational processes.

Universities, under the Law on Higher Education, are independent higher education institutions, which can carry out academic, and/or vocational/applied study programmes at each of the three levels of study. Faculties and art academies are constituent parts of universities and – albeit separate legal entities - cannot exist independently. Both faculties and art academies can carry out academic and/or vocational/applied study programmes at all of the three levels of study. University integrates the functions of all of its constituent institutions and units - notably faculties - through unified policies aimed at the on-going promotion of the quality of courses and improvement of scientific research and artistic creativity.

¹<https://eurydice.eacea.ec.europa.eu/national-education-systems/serbia/types-higher-education-institutions>

A **College of academic studies** is an independent higher education institution entitled to organise and conduct only first and second-cycle study programmes (Bachelor and Master academic studies).

A **College of applied studies** is an independent higher education institution entitled to organise first and second-cycle study programmes (vocational studies at Bachelor, Master and specialised levels).

The **Academy of applied studies** is an institution that integrates several vocational study colleges that is undergoing an institutional change.

In the ETER reports, a slightly different categorization is applied, which is adapted to ongoing changes in the Serbian HEI system. Dedicated vocational colleges (both public and private) are seen as important categories of the Serbian HEI system and are specifically featured in ETER. In addition, in comparison to the previous report (referring to 2019 data), this report (reference year 2020) comprises two additional categories of HEIs: The “Private Faculty that is not part of the university”, and the “State Academy of Vocational Studies”, the latter gathering 10 institutions that were newly established in 2020 and formerly were part of the “State Vocational Colleges” sector.

Main institutional characteristics. Legal status and the right to award a PhD

Table 1 provides a quantitative overview of the main institutional characteristics of Serbian HEIs. As mentioned in the previous section, Serbian universities are categorized in two main categories, private and public ones (Private University and State University). These two categories are unchanged, i.e., 9 State and 8 Private Universities from 2019 to 2020. Both State and Private Universities are all PhD awarding, this being a pre-condition to get the legal status of a university as described in the previous section. A new establishment is the above-mentioned “Private Faculty that is not part of the university”, which is not entitled to award PhDs. The vocational HEI sector has undergone substantial structural change, according to ETER data: in terms of the number of institutions, State Vocational Colleges have been reduced from 26 to 7 in 2020, while one Private Vocational College was created in this year, and 10 new institutions were created under the roof of the State Academy of vocational studies, all non-PhD awarding.

Table 1. Institutional type and legal status by HEI type, 2020

Category		N	Public	Private	PhD awarding
Private Faculty that is not part of the university	Приватни факултет који није у саставу универзитета	1	0	1	0
Private University	Приватни универзитет	9	0	9	9
Private Vocational College	Приватна висока струковна школа	5	0	5	0

Category		N	Public	Private	PhD awarding
State Academy of vocational studies	Државна академија струковних студија	10	10	0	0
State University	Државни универзитет	8	8	0	8
State Vocational College	Државна висока струковна школа	7	7	0	0
Total		40	25	15	17

Note: Numbers reflect inclusion in ETER

Institutional history. Older and younger institutional types

Data on the HEI foundation year provide information on the history of Serbia's higher education and its evolution over time.

Figure 1 shows that the expansion of the system in terms of the number of HEIs is relatively recent. Interestingly, State Vocational Colleges have substantially been introduced between the 1960s and 1980s during the former Socialist Federal Republic of Yugoslavia (1963–1992). The oldest Serbian university (University of Belgrade) dates back to 1905, also given that Serbia as an independent state was just admitted in the late 19th century. Until the 1960s, we can observe only three more State Universities that have been established, while we see a significant increase between 1960 and 1980 related to the socio-economic development of Serbia as core of Yugoslavia. During the years of the Balkan war, we can see a stagnation of further HEI establishments, while with the proclamation of the Republic of Serbia and after the war ended, a steady growth of newly founded HEIs can be observed. In particular, we can identify a significant growth of Private Universities, with the first ones occurring in 2000, and already overtaking in numbers the State Universities in 2008. Finally, in 2020, we observe the foundation of the State Academy of vocational studies, which has started to play a major role in Serbia's vocational HEI sector.

Figure 1. Foundation year of HEIs by type

Students

While State Universities and Private Universities are almost equal in terms of the number of entities, State Universities massively outpace Private Universities but also State and Private Vocational Colleges in terms of the number of students enrolled (Figure 2). Actually, State Universities account for 73% of all students enrolled in the year 2020. This skewed distribution is even more pronounced for higher ISCED levels, i.e., accounting for more than 87% for master students, and even 97% for PhD students. The latter underlines the substantial role of State Universities in a research context, while Private Universities play a very small role there. State Academy of vocational studies and Private Universities have their largest contributions with Bachelor-level education (around 13% of the students) but are still way behind universities. In comparison, Private Vocational Colleges are almost negligible in terms of the number of students enrolled.

Figure 2. Students by level and type of HEI, 2020

Note: Total students include ISCED 5-7

Personnel

People are a core resource for HEIs, as their competences are essential for teaching, undertaking research and producing scientific output. In that respect, ETER seeks to provide a rich set of data moving beyond the information available in EUROSTAT, which allows to analyze the composition of personnel by type of HEI and characteristics such as gender, nationality, educational field and, from 2020 onwards, levels of seniority. For Serbia's HEI system, personnel data are only available on academic personnel and research and teaching assistants.

As shown in Figure 3, State Universities employ the 78% of all personnel of the Serbian higher education system, while Private Universities account for 11%, and the State Academy of vocational studies for further 8% of the total academic and assistant staff. There are also major differences between these HEI types in size, as measured by total personnel in full time equivalents (FTE), and in the personnel composition. With an average of about 1,400 FTEs, State Universities are significantly larger than Private Universities (172 FTE). In terms of the personnel composition, the shares of academic personnel on the one hand and research and teaching assistants on the other, are quite similar across the institutional types, with roughly 75% of the staff being academic personnel.

Figure 3. Personnel (FTE) by category and type of HEI, 2020

Note: Support and administrative personnel is missing.

Changing roles over time

Figure 4 illustrates changes over time in terms of students enrolled between 2013 and 2020 (no data for 2011 and 2012). We can observe a slight growth between the years 2014 and 2015, but then a steady decline until 2019 of about 8000 students (nearly a 10% decline of the 2016 total). This may be an indication of an increasing number of students that prefers to study abroad, a similar observation in many Central and Eastern European countries. Concerning the distribution between the Public and Private Universities no significant changes have occurred since 2016 (with Public Universities around 75% of total students enrolled). For State Vocational Colleges (no data for 2013-2015), there is a clearly decreasing trend, both in absolute numbers and in shares of total students. With the advent of the State Academy of vocational studies in 2020, accounting for 12% of all higher education students in Serbia, we observe a rise of 5% in the total number of higher education students as compared with the previous year.

Figure 4 Share of students enrolled by institutional type, 2013-2020

Note Data missing for Private vocational college and State vocational college before 2016. Data missing for Private Faculty that is not part of the university and State Academy of vocational studies missing before 2020

As shown by Figure 5, the number of academic personnel in Serbian HEIs was quite stable over the years from 2013 to 2020, irrespective of the decreasing number of students. Only in 2020, with the introduction of the

State Academy of vocational studies, the data show a 6% increase in total academic personnel (FTE) in Serbian HEIs (as compared with 2016), keeping pace with the expansion in the number of students in this year.

Figure 5 Academic personnel (FTE) by type of HEI, 2013-2020

Note Data missing for Private vocational college and State vocational college before 2016. Data missing for Private Faculty that is not part of the university and State Academy of vocational studies missing before 2020

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